

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

The Impact of Contextual Information on the Fairness of Deep Knowledge Tracing

METADATA_FAIRNESS_DKT

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	
Version:	1.0
Status:	
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	

The Impact of Contextual Information on the Fairness of Deep Knowledge Tracing has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the “The Impact of Contextual Information on the Fairness of Deep Knowledge Tracing” project. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [2-7] sections.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by parties of the “The Impact of Contextual Information on the Fairness of Deep Knowledge Tracing” project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From:			
Moderated by:			
Reviewed by:			
Approved by:			

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	[28.04.2025]		

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

CONTRIBUTORS

Role	Persons
Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	
Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	Paula-Elena Gheorghe, e11926306@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien
Contributors	Paula-Elena Gheorghe, e11926306@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, Data Manager

The starting template of this DMP was generated using a tool provided by the Technical University of Vienna: <https://dmptool.tuwien.ac.at/>. Some of the sample texts provided by the platform were used in this document as well.

This DMP has the following DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.15299382.

Content

1. Executive Summary	5
1.1. Introduction	5
1.2. Data Summary	5
1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse	5
1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users:	6
2. FAIR data	6
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	6
2.2. Making data accessible	6
2.3. Making data interoperable	7
2.4. Increase data re-use	8
3. Other research outputs	8
4. Allocation of resources	9
5. Data security	9
5.1. Storage and backup facilities	10
5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data	10
5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data	10
6. Ethical and legal issues	11
6.1. Personal data	11
6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership	11
6.3. Ethical issues	11
7. Other issues	11

1 Executive Summary

1.1 Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Paula-Elena Gheorghe (e11926306@student.tuwien.ac.at) will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2 Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	synthetic_student_data_fast_learners	Structured text		100 - 1000 MB	no
P2	synthetic_student_data_fast_learners_with_metadata	Structured text		100 - 1000 MB	no
P3	synthetic_student_data_slow_learners	Structured text		100 - 1000 MB	no
P4	synthetic_student_data_slow_learners_with_metadata	Structured text		100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "synthetic_student_data_fast_learners":

Synthetic student data of fast learning students

Description for "synthetic_student_data_fast_learners_with_metadata":

Synthetic student data of fast learners, with metadata

Description for "synthetic_student_data_slow_learners":

Synthetic student data of slow learning students

Description for "synthetic_student_data_slow_learners_with_metadata":

Synthetic student data of slow learning students, with metadata

There are also anonymized real-world datasets mentioned at section [1.3], but which were preprocessed, so not used directly as they were. They were not used in the assignment's use case, but in the Bachelor's thesis they were used as another dataset for the experiments, alongside the synthetically generated one. All the data files are in .csv format. The purpose of using varied datasets was to verify the machine learning model's effectiveness in making correct predictions using different types of input data.

1.3 Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Some datasets were generated synthetically by using a script, and other datasets which already existed and contained real-world data were modified, by using another script. The source of the real-world dataset is mentioned at <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2104.04034>, which is <https://eedi.com/projects/neurips-education-challenge>, which in turn references <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2007.12061>.

1.4 Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community, and potentially students and other University-affiliated researchers

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in the respective GitHub repository and include a timestamp of upload or modification. Version control is automated

CodeMeta (<https://codemeta.github.io/>) is used for generating metadata about the software and which is to be included in the GitHub repository. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data. One notable keyword for finding the repository is “deep knowledge tracing”.

The code repository can be found at: https://github.com/pghgh/impact_of_contextual_information_on_fairness_of_dkt_dsw_ue_25ss.git

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The synthetic data, code and outputs are available for the public, but the modified real-world datasets or the original datasets themselves could not be uploaded to the GitHub repository or to DBRepo, because of the license chosen by the authors, namely "Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0)". No embargo was applied to the data release.

There are also no restrictions when using the data uploaded on DBRepo, and the data can also be accessed after the assignment is finished. The only committee which was needed was to approve the upload of research data on TUWRD.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-04-25			CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open		2025-04-25			CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open		2025-04-25			CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open		2025-04-25			CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Data can already be accessed free of charge from <https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/c45328ec-80f7-497d-8be6-c3505489ddb4/info>, but can also generate it using a script provided in the GitHub repository. The data containing plots of one run of the experiments can be found at <https://test.researchdata.tuwien.ac.at/records/xsycq-b6m84>.

The code metadata file, “codemeta.json”, uploaded on GitHub, is released under the MIT license, just like the rest of the files. The metadata will not exist anymore if the repository gets deleted.

2.3 Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. Descriptions about the synthetic datasets were provided. Further usage of ontologies is not planned. The usage of adapted datasets was documented in the DMP but also in the GitHub repository.

2.4 Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology,

codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

The license chosen for the synthetically generated datasets, namely “Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)”, facilitate data reuse. Regarding the modified real-world datasets, it is mentioned in the GitHub repository that neither the original files nor the adapted ones were uploaded to the repository because of the chosen license, but scripts can be run so that the same modified datasets can be obtained by other users.

The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.

3 Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

There is no other research output identified for this project up until the moment of writing the DMP.

4 Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Coverage of costs:

All the data should be kept as long as possible, since there is no legal requirement for this data to be taken down after a point.

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with the teams behind GitHub, DBRepo and TUWRD being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5 Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1 Storage and backup facilities

The synthetic datasets will be stored on the test instance of DBRepo. This is a type of institutional storage, provided by the Technical University of Vienna.

5.2 Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any further sensitive data in the project, because the real-world data was already anonymized. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	reading only	reading only	reading only
P2	reading only	reading only	reading only
P3	reading only	reading only	reading only
P4	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3 Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	DBRepo test instance: https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/c45328ec-80f7-497d-8be6-c3505489ddb4/table/625517fd-7a16-4827-a21b-527cbc20a06c/info	10 years
P2	DBRepo test instance: https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/c45328ec-80f7-497d-8be6-c3505489ddb4/table/bd5437a4-8a02-4f2a-a07e-71e8b86db430/info	10 years
P3	DBRepo test instance: https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/c45328ec-80f7-497d-8be6-c3505489ddb4/table/748f5788-47f9-41e1-94e5-88d1612c17dc/info	10 years
P4	DBRepo test instance: https://test.dbrepo.tuwien.ac.at/database/c45328ec-80f7-497d-8be6-c3505489ddb4/table/22292e16-8f3f-4ef7-9578-5420896af32f/info	10 years

6 Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1 Personal data

In this project, I modified datasets containing anonymized data about students' personal data.

6.2 Intellectual property rights and rights of use

There are legal restrictions on how data is processed or shared. The legal restrictions are based on the following license: "Attribution 4.0 International" (CC BY 4.0).

6.3 Ethical issues

Ethical issues in the project have not yet been identified or discussed with the Service Unit of Responsible Research Practices at TU Wien (www.tuwien.at/research-ethics), since there might also be none.

7 Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No, we will not make use of such procedures.